

THE PRINCIPLE OF SEPARATION OF POWERS - AS A GUARANTEE OF JUDICIAL INDEPENDENCE

Dauletmuratov Timur Dauletmuratovich

law teacher of the Nukus "Temurbeklar Maktabi" lyceum of the Ministry of
Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan
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Annotation: This article analyzes the legal guarantees based on the principle of independence of the judiciary and the principle of separation of powers between branches of government. In particular, the constitutional and legislative foundations aimed at ensuring judicial independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan, reforms in the judicial system, as well as factors threatening the independence of judges are highlighted. The article discusses the independence of the judiciary not only within the framework of the domestic legal system, but also based on international experience. Also presented are proposals for the phased implementation of judicial reforms, problems in the formation of an independent judicial system, and their elimination.

Keywords: judicial independence, principle of separation of powers, legal reforms, judicial system, constitutional guarantees, rights of judges, rule of law, fair trial, rule of law, international experience.

The independence of the judiciary primarily means that all relations between branches of government must be built solely on the basis and within the framework of the law. In particular, one of the important requirements of a legal state, the principle of separation of powers, is aimed at ensuring the independence of each branch of government, including the judiciary[1,37 p].

First and foremost, fully ensuring judicial independence must be one of our most important tasks. I would like to reiterate that the ongoing violations of the law during the preliminary investigation can only be rectified by achieving the true independence of the courts[2].

The status of judges may be changed only in the manner prescribed by law. Thus, the executive branch cannot make any decisions regarding the material or other rewards of courts at the central or local levels. Certain aspects of these issues (the procedure for their resolution) are directly defined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Articles 130-140) and special laws ("On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan," "On Courts," and others). The independence of the courts in our country is enshrined in the Constitution of our Republic. Specifically, Article 130 states that "In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the judiciary operates independently of the legislative and

executive branches, political parties, and other public associations." A similar rule can be found in Article 1 of the Law "On Courts" (new edition).

Continuing the above, it is appropriate to cite the following norm enshrined in Article 66 of the Law "On Courts" (interference in the resolution of court cases is not permitted): "Interference in the work of judges in the administration of justice is not permitted." Influencing judges in any way to obstruct a comprehensive, complete, and impartial review of a specific case or to obtain an illegal court decision entails criminal liability in accordance with the law.

Despite the existence of a number of norms aimed at guaranteeing the independence of judges, in practice, there are still negative instances of interference in the duties of judges by certain state bodies and officials. Specifically, in judicial and investigative practice, judges may be influenced by the prosecutor, investigator, criminal, their relatives, or other participants in the crime who remain in custody, as well as other participants in the process. The Criminal Code (Article 236 - Interference in the investigation or the resolution of court cases) provides certain guarantees regarding this. Furthermore, they pose a significant threat to the independence of judges, prosecutors, and investigators, as well as officials at various levels who strive to ensure the issuance of relevant verdicts and other court decisions for themselves. The main goal is to create new mechanisms for the effective protection of judges, prosecutors, and investigators from such incidents. In this regard, using the experience of foreign countries, it is necessary to ensure that, if necessary, measures are taken to protect the life, health, relatives, and property of judges. As L.M.Entin noted, "studying the experience of foreign countries in ensuring the independence of the judiciary plays a leading role in a positive solution to the problem"[3, 174 p].

European ideologists, in particular, Lökk, Russo, Monteske, and Kelzen, were engaged in the development of a model of a legal society based on the principles of sovereignty of the people, protection of fundamental human rights, separation of powers, and the rule of law. To ensure equality between branches of government and at the same time protect the fundamental rights of citizens, judicial guarantees are necessary, because only judicial protection could ensure the implementation of these rights[4, 39 p].

Large-scale reforms aimed at ensuring the true independence of the courts and the rule of law are being implemented consistently[5].

As a result of ensuring judicial independence, 1,244 citizens were acquitted in 2023, and in 2024 alone, acquittals were issued against 723 citizens[6].

Based on the foregoing, it can be said that the issue of judicial independence is a significant educational and psychological problem, as "in many complex situations, a judge's personal qualities, their understanding of their civic and professional duties, and their ability to resist unlawful influence are of decisive importance"[7].

Not only in Uzbekistan, but in all modern democratic countries (such as the USA, Germany, France), justice operates independently of other branches of government. In accordance with the principle of separation of powers, the main purpose of which is the restoration of violated rights and the proper implementation of laws, the court carries out justice within the framework established at the level of the Constitution and is considered an independent and sovereign authority.

With the help of judicial processes, it will be possible to most justly determine the boundaries of freedom and obligations of citizens in relations between other persons, society and the state. The constructive role of the judiciary is particularly evident in the US, where judges and courts have extensive jurisdictional oversight capabilities[8]. About the USA, A. Tokvil wrote a century and a half ago: "There are practically no political issues in the United States that do not become a matter of law"[9].

The powers granted to American courts to comment on the inadequacy of laws are clearly defined, which is the greatest obstacle to the oppression of the political system.

The independence of the courts is rooted in the separation of powers in a democratic society. Various state bodies have special and specific powers. The judicial system, as an institution, and judges should have exclusive powers in the consideration of cases within their competence.

First of all, it should be noted that its phased implementation is an important feature of judicial and legal reforms in Uzbekistan. Admittedly, the historical development of these stages is described differently. Some scholars link the beginning of the first stage to the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 1992, while the second stage is linked to the adoption of the Law "On Courts" in September 1993, as well as the new Criminal Code and the Criminal Procedure Code. The third modern stage of deepening judicial and legal reforms began in 2000, during which a new edition of the Law "On Courts" and a number of other new laws were adopted.

Specifically, A.X. Saidov refers to the period before Perestroika as the first stage[10, 11 p]. The judiciary was not considered an independent body. In

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conditions where the theory of the separation of powers was not recognized, the courts were considered an integral part of the unified Soviet government, meaning their powers were significantly limited. For a long time, the functions previously belonging to the courts were assigned to various administrative bodies. In a number of cases, this led to gross violations of human rights.

Courts did not have the right to resolve disputes arising from the actions of collegial bodies and officials. Labor rights of many groups of workers could not be protected in court, there was no judicial control over the protection of human rights at the time of the preliminary investigation, etc.

There were many bodies with state administrative powers, and their decisions could not be appealed in court. Specifically, in the relationship between the courts and the prosecutor's office, the prosecutor's office held a significant advantage.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the specialization of courts played an important role in reforming the judicial system, namely, the division of courts of general jurisdiction into courts for separate consideration of civil and criminal cases. This decree has contributed to strengthening guarantees of citizens' rights and freedoms and more fully ensuring the quality and timely consideration of court cases. The reform of the judicial system with the aim of establishing fully independent courts, improving the quality and speed of administration of justice, ensuring the fairness of court decisions, as well as the adoption of a new version of the Law "On Courts" at the IV session of the second convocation of the Oliy Majlis on December 14, 2000, determined the need for this. Subsequently, a number of important reforms were implemented in the judicial and legal sphere, and the current Law "On Courts" was adopted on July 28, 2021.

In the process of implementing judicial reforms, the powers of the courts have been fundamentally changed, namely: from the norms limited by laws and regulations in the sphere of civil, criminal, and administrative legal relations, a corresponding scope of powers has been established in accordance with the rules of procedure adopted in the world. The expansion of the powers of the courts has made it possible for them to become an equal branch of state power, which has given the court the opportunity to protect the rights and freedoms of people, the values of civil society.

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